

EELISA

European University

OVERVIEW OF EELISA INNOVATION TALKS (1)

Deliverable 7.6

Date: 30 November, 2022

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

Technical references

Grant Agreement number:	101035811
Project Acronym:	EELISA InnoCORE
Project title:	EELISA INNOVation and COmmon REsearch strategy
Start date of the project:	1 June 2021
Duration of the project:	36 months

Deliverable No.:	7.6 Overview of EELISA innovation talks (1)
Work Package:	7
Task:	7.4 EELISA innovation talks
Lead beneficiary:	FAU
Due date of deliverable:	30 November 2022
Actual submission date:	30 November 2022
Dissemination level:	Public

Document history

Version	Date	WP Leader	Reviewed by:
0.1	17 November 2022	FAU	First draft by David Schkade (FAU)
0.2	22 November 2022	FAU	Second draft modified following input from EELISA InnoCORE partners
0.3	24 November 2022	FAU	First quality check by Antoine Mercier (PSL)
0.4	28 November 2022	FAU	Second quality check by EELISA Executive Board, EELISA Executive Director (Sofia Costa d'Aguiar), EELISA InnoCORE quality assurance coordinator (Juan Manuel Muñoz)
1.0	30 November 2022	FAU	Final version by David Schkade (FAU)

Acknowledgement: This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

Disclaimer: The European Commission support for the production of this publication does not constitute an endorsement of the contents which reflects the views only of the authors, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.

EELISA InnoCORE Partners

Number	Role	Name in original language	Name in English	Short name	Country
1	COO	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	Technical University of Madrid	UPM	Spain
2	BEN	École Nationale des Ponts et Chaussées	National School of Civil Engineering	ENPC	France
3	BEN	Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg	Friedrich-Alexander University Erlangen-Nürnberg	FAU	Germany
4	BEN	İstanbul Teknik Üniversitesi	Istanbul Technical University	ITU	Turkey
5	BEN	Scuola Normale Superiore	Higher Normal School	SNS	Italy
6	BEN	Scuola Superiore di Studi Universitari e di Perfezionamento Sant'Anna	Sant'Anna School of Advanced Studies	SSSA	Italy
7	BEN	Universitatea Politehnica din Bucuresti	Politehnica University of Bucharest	UPB	Romania
8	BEN	Budapesti Műszaki és Gazdaságtudományi Egyetem	Budapest University of Technology and Economics	BME	Hungary
9	BEN	Université Paris Sciences et Lettres	Université PSL	PSL	France

Alliance members

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

Executive summary

This document is prepared within the work package WP7 – “Create the ‘embedding’ for EELISA-wide R & I structures (Optimize outreach)”, as deliverable D7.6 “Overview of EELISA innovation talks (1)” of the project EELISA INNOVation and COmmon REsearch strategy (hereinafter referred to as EELISA InnoCORE), co-funded by European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 101035811.

The document gives an overview of EELISA Innovation Talks (1) including conclusions from events held with the number of live attendees and evaluation of media distribution (hit rates etc.). The reporting period for this overview of EELISA Innovation Talks (1) spans from their conception before the end of May 2022, through their launch in June 2022, to the end of the first reporting period in November 2022. EELISA Innovation Talks were first conceptualized in task 7.4 and further elaborated with the aim to bring the knowledge generated in EELISA to the broader public while making EELISA a vibrant forum for innovation and Europe, and the world, a better place. These are the main goals of this monthly event series that gives the stage to our best EELISA researchers and innovators to discuss the possibilities, risks, and opportunities of technology and innovation for sustainable development. Each session is hosted by a different EELISA institution and streamed to the world on the EELISA YouTube channel from Madrid, Paris, Pisa, Erlangen, Nuremberg, Budapest, Bucharest, or Istanbul. Each partner institution can choose from a variety of appealing formats such as panel discussions, live talks, live interviews, or any other interactive format. In the first reporting period, EELISA Innovation Talks were hosted by BME, FAU, UPB, SNS, and SSSA on a variety of topics related to innovation and allowed for some first insights into the respective innovation ecosystems as well as into the challenges and opportunities they respectively we are facing.

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

Responsibles for EELISA Innovation Talks under EELISA InnoCORE

Partner	Acronym	Contact person for EELISA Innovation Talks
Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	UPM	Claudio Feijoo (claudio.feijoo@upm.es) Isabel Salgueiro (isabel.salgueiro@upm.es) Elena Berga (elena.bmontardit@upm.es)
École Nationale des Ponts et Chaussées	ENPC	Charlotte Huber (charlotte.huber@enpc.fr)
Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg	FAU	David Schkade (david.schkade@fau.de)
İstanbul Teknik Üniversitesi	İTÜ	Mehmet Ercek (ercekme@itu.edu.tr)
Scuola Normale Superiore	SNS	Chiara Cappelli (chiara.cappelli@sns.it) Claudia Giua (claudia.giua@sns.it)
Scuola Superiore di Studi Universitari e di Perfezionamento Sant'Anna	SSSA	Monia Gentile (monia1.gentile@santannapisa.it) Elisa Guidi (elisa.guidi@santannapisa.it) Fatimata Pietra (Fatimata.Pietra@santannapisa.it)
Universitatea Politehnica din Bucuresti	UPB	Ciprian Dobre (ciprian.dobre@upb.ro) Radu Ciobanu (radu.ciobanu@upb.ro)
Budapesti Műszaki és Gazdaságtudományi Egyetem	BME	Attila Joó (jo.attila@emk.bme.hu) Zsolt Gémesi (gemesi.zsolt@bme.hu)
Université Paris Sciences et Lettres	PSL	Antoine Mercier (antoine.mercier@chimieparistech.psl.eu)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

Glossary - Abbreviations and definitions

(alphabetic order)

CA. Consortium Agreement. The consortium agreement is a private agreement between the beneficiaries, to set out the rights and obligations amongst themselves. (It does NOT involve the European Commission/Agency.)

Communication. Taking strategic and targeted measures for promoting the action itself and its research outputs to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public, and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange.

Dissemination. The public disclosure of the research outputs by any appropriate means, including by scientific publications in any medium.

Exploitation. The utilisation of research outputs in further research activities other than those covered by the action concerned, or in developing, creating and marketing a product or process, or in creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities.

EELISA Community. The EELISA communities are mission-driven working groups that bring together students, teachers, and researchers from all partner universities with prestigious professionals, grassroots organizations, citizens, private companies, and public institutions to find innovative solutions to real-world challenges.

EELISA Cluster. EELISA Clusters are science-based working groups that will work on the scientific and technological solutions that may contribute to solve the societal challenges identified by EELISA Communities.

EELISA Innovation Talks. EELISA Innovation Talks aim to raise the public awareness – and thus also the scientific awareness – for the knowledge generated in EELISA and are publicly visible events and fora for discussion in the real and digital world. The events shall thematise the use of technology and innovation for sustainable development and develop a strong brand of EELISA for a broader public. EELISA Innovation Talks are an event series set up by EELISA InnoCORE.

GA. Grant Agreement. This is the grant contract concluded between the EU and the beneficiaries. It establishes the rights and obligations that govern the grant. It consists of a core text and annexes (for instance, fixing the project content and the project budget).

Project Results/ Project Outputs. By project results we understand a unit of knowledge that has been generated out of a project. This includes any tangible or intangible output of the action, such as data, prototypes, demonstrators, knowledge and information whatever their form or nature, whether or not they can be protected. It is not limited to pioneering discoveries, but may also include new methodologies/processes, adaptations, insights, alternative applications of prior knowledge. Along this document, we use project results and project outputs indistinctively, with the same meaning.

R & I. Research and Innovation

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

Table of Contents

Technical references.....	2
Document history	2
EELISA InnoCORE Partners.....	3
Executive summary.....	4
Responsibles for EELISA Innovation Talks under EELISA InnoCORE.....	5
Glossary - Abbreviations and definitions	6
Table of Contents.....	7
1 Introduction to EELISA InnoCORE.....	8
2 General considerations	10
2.1 The concept of EELISA Innovation Talks and its implementation.....	11
2.1.1 The concept of EELISA Innovation Talks according to task 7.4 and its further elaboration.....	11
2.1.2 The implementation of the concept of EELISA Innovation Talks	14
2.2 Overview of EELISA Innovation Talks (1)	17
2.2.1 EELISA Innovation Talk # 1 hosted by BME	18
2.2.2 EELISA Innovation Talk # 2 hosted by FAU.....	19
2.2.3 EELISA Innovation Talk # 3 hosted by UPB.....	22
2.2.4 EELISA Innovation Talk # 4 hosted by SNS.....	24
2.2.5 EELISA Innovation Talk # 5 hosted by SSSA.....	26
2.2.6 Summary overview of the on-site and online participation in all EELISA Innovation Talks during the first reporting period.....	28

List of tables

Table 1: List of work packages and WP leaders.....	9
Table 2: Summary overview of the on-site and online participation in all EELISA Innovation Talks during the first reporting period.....	28

List of figures

Figure 1: General event banner for EELISA Innovation Talks	14
Figure 2: Example of the individual event banner for EELISA Innovation Talks.....	15
Figure 3: Event banner for EELISA Innovation Talk # 1 hosted by BME	18
Figure 4: Event banner for EELISA Innovation Talk # 2 hosted by FAU	20
Figure 5: Event banner for EELISA Innovation Talk # 3 hosted by UPB.....	23
Figure 6: Event banner for EELISA Innovation Talk # 4 hosted by SNS.....	24
Figure 7: Event banner for EELISA Innovation Talk # 5 hosted by SSSA.....	26

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

1 Introduction to EELISA InnoCORE

The European Engineering Learning Innovation and Science Alliance (EELISA) is a bottom-up alliance of European higher education institutions representing more than 180,000 students and 50,000 graduates each year, 16,000 faculty members and 11,000 administrative staff. EELISA is one of the 45 European Universities selected by the European Commission under the Erasmus+ call, focused on education. EELISA was selected during the second pilot call. With the formalization of this European University, partners are initiating an unprecedented level of institutionalised cooperation between our institutions in order to gradually achieve our long-term ambitious vision: the education of European Engineers.

A pillar of EELISA will be the setting-up of EELISA Communities: challenge-based working groups where citizens, private companies and academia will collaborate to face societal challenges. EELISA Communities will be the place where education, research, innovation and public debate coexist and connect, enhancing the connection of engineering with society.

Within this framework, **EELISA InnoCORE is conceived as an integral part of the Alliance**, being a tool supporting, strengthening and delving deeper into the cooperation set up by EELISA. Building on the ecosystem of EELISA Communities, **EELISA InnoCORE focuses on the R&I dimension of the Alliance in a three-step plan**: 1) make our researchers and innovators know each other, create spaces for dialogue with citizens and with non-academic actors and set up a portfolio of shared scientific infrastructures; 2) foster and support the development of joint R&I actions and the creation of new structures (research groups, clusters, joint labs, start-ups, scientific parks) and 3) optimize the outreach of these actions.

EELISA InnoCORE will be running for three years and it is structured around seven (7) work packages (WPs), focusing each on one of the key elements of the project. Under InnoCORE, EELISA partners will work on establishing a portfolio of joint research areas and defining a joint roadmap of research infrastructures (WP2). InnoCORE will map existing research infrastructures and facilities (WP4), with two aims: establishing the rules for opening their use and defining the main features of a booking system so that these resources can be used by all researchers of the Alliance, on the one hand; eventually, establishing a framework for jointly investing in new infrastructures.

EELISA InnoCORE will support the collaboration and the setting-up of joint research projects among the members of the Alliance through the development of a networking platform (WP5), the setting-up of clusters¹, the launching of seed funding for prospective young researchers (WP5) and the use of existing or new equipment and facilities in labs to foster collaborations (WP4). In addition to this, EELISA InnoCORE has two work packages dedicated to interlinking the incubation, start-up and entrepreneurship support services of the members of the alliance (WP7) and to foster the participation of society in science (WP7) and strengthening relations with the industry world (WP6). UPM will coordinate and lead the management of the project, being responsible for guiding the project in cross-cutting issues, such as gender balance (WP1). Lastly, the project has a dedicated work package on open science (WP3).

¹ Science-based working groups that will work on scientific and technological solutions than can help solve the societal challenges identified by EELISA Communities.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

WP	WP title	WP Leader
WP1	Coordination, evaluation, communication and dissemination	UPM
WP2	EELISA Research and Innovation Strategy	ITÜ
WP3	EELISA Strategic Framework for Open Science practices	UPB
WP4	EELISA Multi Labs (sharing facilities & equipment)	PSL
WP5	Set up initiatives for joint research projects (Enable joint research)	SNS
WP6	Reinforcing cooperation in R&I with other sectors, especially academia-business cooperation	BME
WP7	Create the "embedding" for EELISA-wide R&I structures (Optimize outreach)	FAU

Table 1: List of work packages and WP leaders

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

2 General considerations

EELISA Innovation Talks pursue the ambitious goal to bring the knowledge generated in EELISA to the broader public while making EELISA a vibrant forum for innovation and Europe, and the world, a better place. In order to achieve this ambitious goal, we have taken the following steps: Firstly, we set up a monthly event series that secondly, gives the stage to our best EELISA researchers and innovators to discuss the possibilities, risks, and opportunities of technology and innovation for sustainable development. Thirdly, we created an easily recognizable EELISA Innovation Talks event banner that is used to promote EELISA Innovation Talks and is updated before each event. Fourthly, we created a general EELISA Innovation Talks event webpage,² where general information about the event series and an overview of the EELISA Innovation Talks held so far can be found. Fifthly, we create event webpages for each individual EELISA Innovation Talk where specific information about each event can be found. Sixthly, we use EELISA media channels for innovation for promoting EELISA Innovation Talks on the central EELISA media channels as well as on the EELISA partners' local media channels. Seventhly, EELISA Innovation Talks are both on site and online events easily accessible to the whole EELISA European University and beyond – no matter if during the event via live stream on YouTube or after the event on the EELISA YouTube channel. Eighthly, EELISA Innovation Talks offer the live audience the possibility to pose their questions to the speakers either on-site or online via comments on YouTube or via other integrated tools such as “slido” that organizers are encouraged to offer to the online-connected audience. Ninthly, when organizing EELISA Innovation Talks each partner institution can choose from a variety of appealing formats such as panel discussions, live talks, live interviews, or any other interactive format that it sees fit the purpose of this event series. Tenthly, apart from this general framework, EELISA Innovation Talks are rotating between the cities of our partnership and it is within the responsibility of each EELISA partner institution to organize their specific EELISA Innovation Talks. This includes the selection of an appealing topic and location, an adequate format, qualified speakers, moderators, and a film team, as well as the general organization and promotion of the event (supported by the EELISA Communication Office and EELISA media channels for innovation). And last but not least, in the first reporting period³ EELISA Innovation Talks were hosted by BME, FAU, UPB, SNS, and SSSA on a variety of topics related to innovation and allowed for some first insights into the respective innovation ecosystems as well as into the challenges and opportunities they respectively we are facing.

In the following, the concept of EELISA Innovation Talks and its implementation are elucidated and an overview of EELISA Innovation Talks (1) is given. This will include an overview of the first conception of EELISA Innovation Talks in EELISA InnoCORE task 7.4 and its further elaboration and implementation as well as an overview of EELISA Innovation Talks (1) providing conclusions from events held with the number of live attendees and evaluation of media distribution (hit rates etc.).

² Cf. <https://eelisa.eu/an-open-stage-for-the-best-eelisa-researchers-and-innovators/>.

³ The first reporting period extends until November 2022. In the upcoming months, that are already part of the second reporting period, EELISA Innovation Talks will be hosted by UPM, ITU, PSL, and ENPC so that until March 2023 each EELISA partner will have hosted a first EELISA Innovation Talk. The second round of EELISA Innovation Talks will start in April 2023. But all of this will be part of the reporting for D7.7 “Overview of EELISA Innovation Talks (2)”.

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

2.1 The concept of EELISA Innovation Talks and its implementation

EELISA Innovation Talks were first conceptualized in EELISA InnoCORE task 7.4 where a general description of the goals and character of EELISA Innovation Talks can be found. For the implementation of EELISA Innovation Talks, we had, however, to further elaborate the concept of EELISA Innovation Talks outlined in task 7.4 and to make some more specific choices. These choices concern (1.) the frequency of EELISA Innovation Talks, (2.) the speakers and topics to be covered by EELISA Innovation Talks, (3.) the promotion material, (4.) the general event webpage, (5.) the specific event webpages, (6.) the use of EELISA media channels for innovation, (7.) the use of the EELISA YouTube channel, (8.) the use of interactive components, (9.) the variety of formats, and (10.) the freedom left to each EELISA partner to organize their EELISA Innovation Talk as they see fit. The following will be an overview of the first conception of EELISA Innovation Talks in task 7.4 and its further elaboration and implementation in the first reporting period up to November 2022.

2.1.1 The concept of EELISA Innovation Talks according to task 7.4 and its further elaboration

The first conception of EELISA Innovation Talks was outlined in the description of EELISA InnoCORE task 7.4, where the following can be found:

“In order to raise the public awareness – and thus also the scientific awareness for the knowledge generated in EELISA – we will set up publicly visible events and fora for discussion in the real and digital world. The events shall thematise the use of technology for sustainable development and develop a strong brand of EELISA for a broader public. We aim at establishing two main (regular) formats that both are held publicly, rotating between the cities of our partnership, and streamed via media channels: a publicly visible panel discussion format, where EELISA scientists discuss current sociotechnological developments with leaders from science, industry and politics, but also with students and participants of civil society. And a second line of interactive formats like fishbowl discussions, science slams or bar camps aiming at a younger audience and established with a strong involvement of young scientists. EELISA Communities – and in particular the results from challenges – will be the main source to feed this activity. We particularly aim at reflecting European topics, referring to the latest European legislation and policy frameworks and regularly inviting experts from European politics, possibly also using and supporting European video platforms. The tasks will further consist in the didactic establishment of formats and moderation (partly with subcontracted professionals), the selection of media channels and cloud archives, publicity and promotion. For this activity, FAU will bring in its large experience in organizing events with public panel discussions (latest example: Weltmarktführer Innovation Day 2020) and the emerging FAU Academy as the shop window for further outreach.”

From this conception, the goal of EELISA Innovation Talks appears to be clear and consists of the following: Raising the public and thus also scientific awareness for the knowledge generated in EELISA by publicly visible events and fora for discussion in the real and digital world which thematise the use of technology for sustainable development and develop a strong brand of EELISA for a broader public. On the general event webpage, we put this much simpler and much more accessible to the public with a slight twist towards innovation: “To bring the knowledge generated in EELISA to the broader public while making EELISA a vibrant forum for innovation and Europe, and the world, a better place. These are the main goals of

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

this monthly event series that will give the stage to our best EELISA researchers and innovators to discuss the possibilities, risks, and opportunities of technology and innovation for sustainable development.” Faced with the challenge of reaching this manifold goal and implementing this general conception of EELISA Innovation Talks, EELISA InnoCORE WP7 representatives discussed various options and finally made several decisions that helped to further elaborate this relatively abstract conception to a more specific one ready for successful implementation:

(1.) We discussed several options and finally decided to set up EELISA Innovation Talks as a monthly event series starting in June 2022 (with a summer break in August of each year). Furthermore, we decided that each EELISA partner will host (at least) two EELISA Innovation Talks during the term of the EELISA InnoCORE project so that we will have (at least) 18 EELISA Innovation Talks in total. Taking both the organizational effort and the demand for an English speaking EELISA Innovation Talks format into account, a thus set up monthly event series seems to be not only feasible but also well balanced. In this way, we further elaborated the concept of EELISA Innovation Talks with regard to their frequency, which was largely left open in the description of task 7.4.

(2.) By contrast, the speakers and topics to be covered by EELISA Innovation Talks were already defined to a large extent in the description of task 7.4: Speakers would include EELISA scientists, leaders from science, industry and politics, experts from European politics, but also students and participants of civil society. Moreover, the topics to be covered would be “the use of technology for sustainable development”, “current socio-technological developments” and the reflection of “European topics, referring to the latest European legislation and policy frameworks”. In the general description of EELISA Innovation Talks on the event webpage, we simplified this by stating that EELISA Innovation Talks “will give the stage to our best EELISA researchers and innovators to discuss the possibilities, risks, and opportunities of technology and innovation for sustainable development. ... We particularly aim at reflecting European topics and perspectives.” The question with whom to discuss these topics is left open as we offer a whole variety of formats from which partners are free to choose, leaving the concentration on “giving the stage to our best EELISA researchers and innovators” the common denominator of all EELISA Innovation Talks.

Concerning (3.) the promotion material, we decided to create a single event banner that is to be updated for each EELISA Innovation Talk and can be used for the event webpage, on social media, and as thumbnail on the EELISA YouTube channel. The event banner shall serve as the public image of EELISA Innovation Talks and shall be the main public relations tool for communicating them. Moreover, we decided to create both (4.) a general event webpage (5.) and specific event webpages. The former shall contain general information about the event series and links to the talks already held. The latter shall contain the specific event information for each individual EELISA Innovation Talk. (6.) Concerning the communication and promotion of EELISA Innovation Talks, we decided to use the EELISA media channels for innovation as developed in EELISA InnoCORE D7.5.

(7.) The description of task 7.4 states that we would “possibly also [be] using and supporting European video platforms” and select “media channels and cloud archives”. With the aim of developing a strong brand of EELISA for a broader public in mind, we chose to generally live stream EELISA Innovation Talks on the EELISA YouTube channel and to make them afterward permanently available there. This decision was taken because the EELISA YouTube

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

channel is already established and promises a broader outreach than other (smaller and less popular) video platforms.

(8.) Furthermore, we came to share the conviction that interactive components would add to the attraction of EELISA Innovation Talks. We thus recommend to all EELISA partners to offer the possibility to the live audience to pose their questions to the speakers both on-site and online via comments on suitable platforms or channels to be chosen.

(9.) Concerning the format of EELISA Innovation Talks, the description of task 7.4 states that we would “aim at establishing two main (regular) formats”: The first one would be “a publicly visible panel discussion format” and the second one would be “a second line of interactive formats like fishbowl discussions, science slams or bar camps”. After deliberation, however, we came to the conclusion that for reaching the goal of EELISA Innovation Talks⁴ (i.e., especially to bring the knowledge generated in EELISA to the broader public, to develop a strong brand of EELISA for a broader public, and to make EELISA a vibrant forum for innovation), it would be sensible to include and try out other formats, that are not explicitly stated in the description of task 7.4, as well. We made a request in this matter to our project officer, who agreed that we could indeed include and try out other formats as well. So finally, we announce on the general EELISA Innovation Talks webpage that our event series “will be developing various appealing formats such as: (1) panel discussions where EELISA scientists discuss current socio-technological developments with leaders from science, industry, and politics, but also with students and participants of civil society; (2) live talks by EELISA researchers and innovators who provide first-hand insights into pressing questions of cutting edge technological developments; (3) live interviews with EELISA researchers, innovators, start-ups, and founders who have made a great contribution to changing the world; (4) any other interactive format like fishbowl discussions, science slams, or bar camps aiming at a younger audience and established with strong involvement of young scientists.”

(10.) Finally, we decided that within this general framework, each EELISA partner institution has the freedom and the responsibility to organize their specific EELISA Innovation Talks as they see fit. This includes the selection of an appealing topic and location, an adequate format, qualified speakers, moderators, and a film team, as well as the general organization and promotion of the event (supported by the EELISA Communication Office and EELISA media channels for innovation).

In such a way, we have further elaborated the concept of EELISA Innovation Talks first outlined in the description of task 7.4. The next step in setting up EELISA Innovation Talks was the implementation of their elaborated concept. This will be outlined in the next section.

⁴ The goal of EELISA Innovation Talks consists in raising the public and thus also scientific awareness for the knowledge generated in EELISA by publicly visible events and fora for discussion in the real and digital world which thematise the use of technology for sustainable development and develop a strong brand of EELISA for a broader public. Or how we put it much simpler and much more accessible to the public with a slight twist towards innovation on the general EELISA Innovation Talks event webpage: “To bring the knowledge generated in EELISA to the broader public while making EELISA a vibrant forum for innovation and Europe, and the world, a better place. These are the main goals of this monthly event series that will give the stage to our best EELISA researchers and innovators to discuss the possibilities, risks, and opportunities of technology and innovation for sustainable development.”

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

2.1.2 The implementation of the concept of EELISA Innovation Talks

In order to achieve the goal of EELISA Innovation Talks, we did not leave it at the conceptual level, but went on to implement the further elaborated concept of EELISA Innovation Talks along the ten conceptual steps:

(1.) Concerning the frequency of EELISA Innovation Talks, we asked partners to choose their slots for hosting their EELISA Innovation Talks as soon as possible and announced on the general event webpage that EELISA Innovation Talks will start in June 2022 and then take place once a month except for summer break in August of each year. In the first reporting period, EELISA Innovation Talks were hosted by BME, FAU, UPB, SNS, and SSSA. In the upcoming months, that are already part of the second reporting period, EELISA Innovation Talks will be hosted by UPM, ITU, PSL, and ENPC so that until March 2023 each EELISA partner will have hosted a first EELISA Innovation Talk. The second round of EELISA Innovation Talks will start in April 2023.

(2.) With regard to the speakers and topics to be covered by EELISA Innovation Talks, we announced on the general event webpage that EELISA Innovation Talks “will give the stage to our best EELISA researchers and innovators to discuss the possibilities, risks, and opportunities of technology and innovation for sustainable development. ... We particularly aim at reflecting European topics and perspectives.” It is within the responsibility of each EELISA partner to implement EELISA Innovation Talks accordingly.

(3.) In order to promote EELISA Innovation Talks, we have created the following general event banner for the general event webpage of EELISA Innovation Talks:

Figure 2: General event banner for EELISA Innovation Talks

In order to promote each individual EELISA Innovation Talk, we additionally create individual event banners whose background design is the same as for the general event banner. The individual event banners contain specific event information and are created at the latest three weeks before each EELISA Innovation Talk by the EELISA Communication Office. The individual event banners are created on the basis of the event information detailed in an event template that the EELISA Communication Office receives at the latest four weeks before the

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

event from the EELISA partner institution responsible for organizing the next EELISA Innovation Talk. The individual event banners are used for event promotion on the event webpage, on social media, and as thumbnail on the EELISA YouTube channel. To illustrate the general design of individual event banners that are updated for each EELISA Innovation Talk, see the following event banner from the EELISA Innovation Talk hosted by FAU as an example:

Figure 2: Example of the individual event banner for EELISA Innovation Talks

(4.) We have created a general event webpage for EELISA Innovation Talks that contains general information about the event series and links to the EELISA Innovation Talks that already took place or will take place soon. This is the link to the general event webpage for EELISA Innovation Talks:

- Link to the general event webpage for EELISA Innovation Talks: <https://eelisa.eu/an-open-stage-for-the-best-eelisa-researchers-and-innovators/>

(5.) Additionally, we have created specific event webpages for each EELISA Innovation Talk that contain the specific event information for each individual EELISA Innovation Talk. Each EELISA partner institution organizing an EELISA Innovation Talk has to send an event template with all the event information needed to the EELISA Communication Office four weeks before the event at the latest. The EELISA Communication Office then creates the specific event webpages including the individual event banners. These are the links to the specific event webpages for EELISA Innovation Talks in the first reporting period from June to November 2022 (with a summer break in August):

- Link to the event webpage of EELISA Innovation Talk # 1 hosted by BME: https://eelisa.eu/events/innovationtalks_session_1/
- Link to the event webpage of EELISA Innovation Talk # 2 hosted by FAU: <https://eelisa.eu/events/eelisa-innovation-talks-2-the-future-of-e-mobility/>
- Link to the event webpage of EELISA Innovation Talk # 3 hosted by UPB: <https://eelisa.eu/events/eelisa-innovation-talks-3-a-business-theory-of-commodities-for-ri-entrepreneurship/>

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

- Link to the event webpage of EELISA Innovation Talk # 4 hosted by SNS: <https://eelisa.eu/events/innovation-talk-session4-the-electron-a-journey-to-discoveries-and-innovation/>
- Link to the event webpage of EELISA Innovation Talk # 5 hosted by SSSA: <https://eelisa.eu/events/innovation-talk-session5-open-innovation-from-lab-to-market/>

(6.) In order to communicate and promote EELISA Innovation Talks effectively, we have implemented the decision to use the EELISA media channels for innovation as developed in EELISA InnoCORE D7.5 in the following way: The organizer of an EELISA Innovation Talk sends the event information, including a link to the event webpage and the event banner, to the EELISA InnoCORE WP7 representatives, to the EELISA Communication Office, and to the EELISA InnoCORE WP1 leader, who is responsible for communication in EELISA InnoCORE. The EELISA InnoCORE WP1 leader in turn sends the event information to the contact points of EELISA partners' local media channels and EELISA WP9 representatives responsible for communication in EELISA. Additionally, the EELISA InnoCORE WP1 leader set up a meeting with the contact points of EELISA partners' local media channels and the EELISA Communication Office to initiate them into the procedure and help improve communication activities so that each EELISA Innovation Talk is promoted not just on the central EELISA media channels, but also on EELISA partners' local media channels.

(7.) As we decided to generally live stream EELISA Innovation Talks on the EELISA YouTube channel and to make them afterwards permanently available there, we had to implement a certain procedure how to do this, because it was not self-evident from the beginning and involved some learning processes both at the central level of the EELISA Communication Office and at the local level of the technical support teams at each EELISA partner institution responsible for live streaming EELISA Innovation Talks. Usually, the owner of a YouTube channel is also the person live streaming an event, but this is not so with the EELISA Innovation Talks where both are disconnected. In order to tackle this problem we have created a tutorial about how to live stream EELISA Innovation Talks on the EELISA YouTube channel, which greatly helped to improve the process of giving the local camera team access to the EELISA YouTube channel. So far, all EELISA Innovation Talks have been live streamed on the EELISA YouTube Channel and are now available there for the public. These are the links to the EELISA YouTube channel, to the EELISA Innovation Talks playlist on the EELISA YouTube channel, and to the YouTube videos of all EELISA Innovation Talks in the first reporting period from June to November 2022 (with a summer break in August):

- Link to the EELISA YouTube channel: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCPyuvBcRzblgYxGKG2afZIQ>
- Link to the EELISA Innovation Talks playlist on the EELISA YouTube channel: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-mg0WWTTNPw&list=PLL20beMSLsd7g5p7RQYm_y_lcXw8i7aZ4
- Link to the YouTube video of EELISA Innovation Talk # 1 hosted by BME: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-mg0WWTTNPw&list=PLL20beMSLsd7g5p7RQYm_y_lcXw8i7aZ4&index=1
- Link to the YouTube video of EELISA Innovation Talk # 2 hosted by FAU: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=7JItXnsFuo&list=PLL20beMSLsd7g5p7RQYm_y_lcXw8i7aZ4&index=2

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

- Link to the YouTube video of EELISA Innovation Talk # 3 hosted by UPB:
https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KxD9RPIHQVs&list=PLL20beMSLsd7g5p7RQYm_y_lcXw8i7aZ4&index=3
- Link to the YouTube video of EELISA Innovation Talk # 4 hosted by SNS:
https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KvJE9qpBsZM&list=PLL20beMSLsd7g5p7RQYm_y_lcXw8i7aZ4&index=4
- Link to the YouTube video of EELISA Innovation Talk # 5 hosted by SSSA:
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=HHJjPx19zj4>

(8.) Since we came to the conviction that interactive components would add to the attraction of EELISA Innovation Talks, we declare on the general event webpage that “[a]ll sessions will allow participants to pose their questions”. We recommend to all EELISA partners to offer the possibility to the live audience to pose their questions to the speakers both on-site and online via comments on YouTube or via the Q&A tool “slido” (available on slido.com). Slido can be easily integrated below the YouTube live stream and allows to pose questions without registration as well as to select and administer them in a simple way.

(9.) On the general event webpage EELISA Innovation Talks promise that “[t]his series will be developing various appealing formats such as: (1) panel discussions where EELISA scientists discuss current socio-technological developments with leaders from science, industry, and politics, but also with students and participants of civil society; (2) live talks by EELISA researchers and innovators who provide first-hand insights into pressing questions of cutting edge technological developments; (3) live interviews with EELISA researchers, innovators, start-ups, and founders who have made a great contribution to changing the world; (4) any other interactive format like fishbowl discussions, science slams, or bar camps aiming at a younger audience and established with strong involvement of young scientists.” Concerning the implementation of this promise, we leave it to the freedom and responsibility of each EELISA partner to choose the format of their EELISA Innovation Talks from these appealing formats and to realize the chosen format in the best possible way.

(10.) Finally, the results from the freedom left to each EELISA partner to organize their EELISA Innovation Talk as they see fit within the general framework that we established (this freedom including the selection of an appealing topic and location, an adequate format, qualified speakers, moderators, etc.) can be seen in the next section: Overview of EELISA Innovation Talks (1).

2.2 Overview of EELISA Innovation Talks (1)

EELISA Innovation Talks being a monthly event series launched in June 2022 (with a summer break in August of each year) were held five times in the first reporting period. The first EELISA Innovation Talk was hosted by BME, the second by FAU, the third by UPB, the fourth by SNS and the fifth by SSSA. In the following, an overview of these EELISA Innovation Talks (1) will be given that provides conclusions from events held with the number of live attendees and evaluation of media distribution (hit rates etc.). Additionally, a final section provides a table summarizing on-site and online participation in all EELISA Innovation Talks during the first reporting period.

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

2.2.1 EELISA Innovation Talk # 1 hosted by BME

The first EELISA Innovation Talk was hosted by BME on 17 June 2022 from 10:00-10:45 (CEST). The topic of the first EELISA Innovation Talk was “Stimulating green technology and social innovation through European collaboration”. Organizers from BME chose the following teaser for the event webpage: “In this EELISA Innovation Talk event, the panel members will be presenting and discussing novel methods of co-creation in support of the European Green Deal, focusing on the good practices and experiences of professionals working with co-creation-based innovation ecosystems.” The topic of this first EELISA Innovation Talk was approached in a panel discussion with a moderator – Borbala Schenk (Chief European Funding Advisor, BME) – and three panel members: Alice Sheppard (Community Manager at Extreme Citizen Science, University College London), Dr. Peter Kaderjak (Director, BME Zero Carbon Hub), and Koen Vervoort (Network Builder, ENoLL – European Network of Living Labs). This EELISA Innovation Talk took place in the context of the online and in-person international networking event “Competence Fair” held by BME on 17 June 2022. To promote the event the following event webpage and event banner were created:

- Link to the event webpage of EELISA Innovation Talk # 1 hosted by BME: https://eelisa.eu/events/innovations_talks_session_1/

Figure 3: Event banner for EELISA Innovation Talk # 1 hosted by BME

The EELISA Innovation Talk hosted by BME featured three panel members with ten-minute presentations and a consequent Q&A part. Attendance was possible both on-site at BME and virtually via the Whova application, and the talks were also streamed live on YouTube.

The first speaker was Alice Sheppard from University College London with the topic “Citizen Science”. In citizen science, several levels of non-expert participation contribute to scientific research through various methods. Accessibility is the key issue here, which means both citizens’ access to research projects and the scientific community’s access to data and results produced by citizens. Sheppard described three examples of citizen science initiatives, where citizens contribute to research by generating data about their environment in a methodological manner. This approach can enable scientists to evaluate environmental issues more reliably.

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

The second speaker was Peter Kaderják from the BME Zero Carbon Hub. He gave a presentation about renewable energy communities. These are local initiatives that meet their own energy needs through green technologies. Unlike energy corporations, locally organized production and consumption communities are more focused on positive societal impact than on making economic profits. An example from Hungary combined local renewable energy production with poverty relief in rural areas. Issues to be tackled by the initiative comprise technical issues (e.g. setting up micro-grids and integrating them into the distribution network), economic issues (e.g. creating a business model that takes into account societal impact), and regulatory issues (changes needed to encourage positive societal impact vs. business profits).

The third speaker was Koen Vervoort from the European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL). Living labs described as open innovation eco-systems with iterative feedback processes aim at creating sustainable impact. The ENoLL currently has more than 160 member institutions. Living labs can provide a framework for e.g. citizen science projects, and support them by providing guidance and best practices. Some examples of ongoing living labs within Hungary were described.

During the Q&A part, the connection of the presented initiatives with EELISA communities was emphasized. The key to success was identified to consist in raising awareness of the projects among citizens and to integrate those citizens that the conducted research is meant for in order to engage in a feedback loop with them.

The EELISA Innovation Talk # 1 hosted by BME is available on the EELISA YouTube channel and has 90 views and one like as of November 2022 (i.e. about five months after the event):

- Link to the YouTube video of EELISA Innovation Talk # 1 hosted by BME: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-mg0WWTTNPw&list=PLL20beMSLsd7g5p7RQYm_y_lcXw8i7aZ4&index=1

There were about 35 live participants, of which about 10-12 followed the event on the Whova app, about three to four followed the event live on YouTube, and about 20 were present on-site. In sum, the event was more frequented on-site than online.

2.2.2 EELISA Innovation Talk # 2 hosted by FAU

The second EELISA Innovation Talk was hosted by FAU on 25 July 2022 from 18:00-19:30 (CEST) in the Aula im Schloss in Erlangen. The topic of this second EELISA Innovation Talk was “The Future of E-Mobility: Great Challenges and Opportunities for European Societies”. Organizers from FAU chose the following teaser for the event webpage: “At the latest with the recent decision of the European Parliament to ban the sale of new cars with combustion engines from 2035, the future of mobility seems to be e-mobility. This poses great challenges and opportunities for European societies. Many jobs still depend on the combustion engine and in the field of e-mobility American and Chinese competitors are challenging the competitiveness of the German and European automotive industries. If Europe is to successfully manage the shift towards a more sustainable future and retain its technology leadership and global competitiveness, the education of European engineers must be adapted to these challenges. In this EELISA Innovation Talk organised by FAU, Prof. Jörg Franke (FAU) will outline the future of e-mobility with its great challenges and opportunities for European societies, addressing European students, researchers, innovators, and the

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

interested public.” The topic of this second EELISA Innovation Talk was spelled out in a talk by Prof. Jörg Franke (the head of the Chair for Manufacturing Automation and Production Systems (FAPS) at the Department of Mechanical Engineering at FAU) with a subsequent moderated Q&A session involving both the on-site and the online- connected live audience. To promote the event the following event webpage and event banner were created:

- Link to the event webpage of EELISA Innovation Talk # 2 hosted by FAU: <https://eelisa.eu/events/eelisa-innovation-talks-2-the-future-of-e-mobility/>

Figure 4: Event banner for EELISA Innovation Talk # 2 hosted by FAU

This about 90 minutes EELISA Innovation Talk, hosted by FAU, featured a talk by Prof. Jörg Franke, the head of the – due to successful third-party funding – largest chair at FAU (Chair for Manufacturing Automation and Production Systems (FAPS) at the Department of Mechanical Engineering). Franke’s talk on “The Future of E-Mobility: Great Challenges and Opportunities for European Societies” was followed by a subsequent moderated Q&A session involving both the on-site and the online-connected live audience on YouTube who made use of their possibility to pose questions via slido.

At the beginning of his talk, Franke pointed to the problem of climate change. In order to tackle this problem, it is a strong mission of his chair to develop and establish technologies for mobility that are emission-free and sustain the environment. From the various research projects at his chair, Franke chose to highlight the Inductive Power Transfer (IPT) technology in his talk. Through IPT technology, electric energy can be transferred via high-frequency magnetic fields from grids into electric cars (without a cable). According to Franke, IPT technology could be the future of interconnecting electric cars with smart electric grids and indeed a key component in the transformation towards e-mobility. If this transformation turned out to be successful, CO2 emissions could be reduced by one-third, simply by replacing internal combustion engines with electric engines. There is a great risk, however, consisting of the emergence of new (mainly American and Chinese) car companies and the falling behind of the well-established European car companies with the massive job losses, that this would

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

entail. Another challenge of this transformation is the enlargement of the range of electric cars to make them more attractive. According to Franke, both the risk and the challenge can be met by IPT technology as a solution that lies in the core competence of the European and German industries (in contrast to other components of cars like batteries, software, etc.).

Franke started the main part of his talk by examining the dependence on oil, air pollution, and climate catastrophe as the main drivers that motivate the transformation toward electric mobility. But how can this transformation succeed? One element is the European Commission's recent ban on cars with internal combustion engines from 2035 onwards. Another measure would be to price the fossil energies by the costs they actually generate (through increasing CO₂ prices). Then it would be too uneconomic to drive diesel or gasoline cars. Additional to the environmental perspective, there is also the perspective of citizens and employees. And here there is increasing global competition in a shrinking market and overall a very risky situation for the European car industry. Franke outlined several important aspects of the rapidly changing automobile market and dared to predict that in ten years there will be less than five operating systems for electric cars, leaving it open who the winners will be (new American and Chinese car companies being among the strongest competitors). As exit barriers are very high, traditional car companies try to slow down the transition to e-mobility, however, at their own and their employees' risk. Franke contrasted this with the success story of Tesla including various technical details such as an enormously high battery endurance (more than one million miles), their own very successful software development, etc. Furthermore, Franke pointed out that electric cars are generally much more energy efficient than combustion engine cars. Concerning the range of cars, Franke asked the question: Wouldn't it be nice if e-cars had a longer or even unlimited reach? He then showed examples from Siemens and Electron who provide IPT technologies that promise to make this possible. Franke went on to explain the IPT technology and gave an overview of IPT test tracks and projects worldwide. At FAPS Franke and his research team try to industrialize IPT technology so that it can be produced and applied on a mass scale. Franke also wants to launch the CLEANTECH Innovation Park – a research center for e-road applications – near Erlangen and Nuremberg. Additionally, a new bachelor and master study program (e-mobility ACES) for educating the e-mobility engineers of the future will be launched at FAU in the winter term of 2022. At the end of his talk, Franke showed two pictures of Manhattan, one with horse carriages and another one with cars, with only 13 years between them, to illustrate how fast a change in technology can be. Franke expects such a change with regard to e-mobility as well.

In the following Q&A session, Franke answered many questions: For example, he explained that although electric engines have been developed in the 19th century already, the internal combustion engine has become so dominant, because oil has been much cheaper than electric energy. Also, he explained in his answer to a question concerning costs, that one kilometer of highway with an IPT system would cost one million Euro which would make 25 billion Euro for the electrification of all highways in Germany (which equals five years of the subsidies of diesel). Franke also made clear that he considers the IPT technology as the last chance to sustain the dominance of German technology in the automotive industry. Finally, Franke made a plea for a European IPT act that would bring Europe to the forefront in shaping the future of e-mobility. Then, Europe, instead of buying batteries elsewhere, could sell IPT infrastructure to the world, help reduce CO₂ emissions and improve the e-mobility experience, and lead its automobile industry to a sustainable future with many jobs secured. Moreover, EELISA could be a suitable platform for common European research projects.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

The EELISA Innovation Talk # 2 hosted by FAU is available on the EELISA YouTube channel and has 521 views, 20 likes, and one comment as of November 2022 (i.e. about four months after the event):

- Link to the YouTube video of EELISA Innovation Talk # 2 hosted by FAU: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=7JltxnsFuo&list=PLL20beMSLsd7g5p7RQYm_yIcXw8i7aZ4&index=2

There were about 60 live participants, of which about 40 followed the event live on YouTube and about 20 were present on-site (although it was one of the hottest days in the summer of 2022). In sum, the event was much more frequented online than on-site and is by now the EELISA Innovation Talk, which has gained by far the most interest on the EELISA YouTube channel.

2.2.3 EELISA Innovation Talk # 3 hosted by UPB

The third EELISA Innovation Talk was hosted by UPB on 30 September 2022 from 16:00-18:30 (CEST) in the Rectorate Building of UPB in Bucharest. The topic of this third EELISA Innovation Talk was “A business theory of commodities for R&I entrepreneurship”. Organizers from UPB chose the following teaser for the event webpage: “Over time, various theories about firms have shaped how companies behave within the market, the fashion of the business ecosystems, the management styles, or organizational cultures. For instance, firms have been perceived as financial and social constructs. In the entrepreneurial world of nonsensical numbers and chaotic competitions, the firm has become a place of processed unfair advantage. In this EELISA Innovation Talk organized by UPB, Dr. George Crețu discusses a new type of practical construct, namely the transactional approach. This aims to position and define the firm as a commodity. Firms are not emotional belongings, social constructs, or cost depositaries; firms are commodities. They are built for sale. The theory may see the wealth assets (financial and business) in a continuous exchange. The main hypothesis is that speeding transformation is an important condition for socio-economic development. In this context, firms should have features for creating the transactional framework. The motto of the presenter, in fact, is “If your firm does not have any value related to the “capital” (formal or informal) market, you have a problem”. This is particularly important for newly started startups and entrepreneurial ventures. The EELISA Innovation Talk targets particularly the Innovation grounds stemming from Academia, with their peculiarities. “In the entrepreneurial business, an emotional framework and hard work are not enough” says the Talk, and we’ll find out more soon...” The topic of this third EELISA Innovation Talk was treated in a talk by Dr. George Cretu (an entrepreneur and investor with many years of experience, connected with UPB and Axiobit). To promote the event the following event webpage and event banner were created:

- Link to the event webpage of EELISA Innovation Talk # 3 hosted by UPB: <https://eelisa.eu/events/eelisa-innovation-talks-3-a-business-theory-of-commodities-for-ri-entrepreneurship/>

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

Figure 5: Event banner for EELISA Innovation Talk # 3 hosted by UPB

This about 90 minutes EELISA Innovation Talk, hosted by UPB, featured a talk by the Romanian entrepreneur and investor George Cretu and integrated a Q&A part with the on-site live audience and the moderator. Attendance was possible in-person at UPB and online via the live stream on the EELISA YouTube channel.

George Cretu made the point that engineering is about changing the world for the better. In order for change for the better to occur, however, research results have to be brought to the market by entrepreneurs through innovative products. Cretu described entrepreneurship as a harsh reality that he claimed was often falsely depicted as being very nice. Especially for Romania, he diagnosed a lack of capital which is key in bringing innovation to the market. Entrepreneurs should consider their firms as commodities and pursue the aim of attracting investors.

For sustained innovation to occur a framework has to be created that supports and professionalizes the creation of startups. This can be done through accelerators. To create an established framework around innovators, UPB is building the BizzSpineTeq – an accelerator that is soon to be launched. So far, no university accelerator exists in Romania. To develop the country and to strengthen the UPB community, the new accelerator at UPB shall help to transfer research into innovation that will be successful on the market and change the world for the better. It was stressed that it should be the mission of UPB to change the current situation of technology transfer for the better in Romania. The event was raising awareness of the problems connected with R&I entrepreneurship in Romania and proposed some concrete solutions to tackle these problems. In the context of EELISA an exchange of best practices and workshops that will help to foster institutional transformation seems to be promising.

The EELISA Innovation Talk # 3 hosted by UPB is available on the EELISA YouTube channel and has 204 views, six likes, and one comment as of November 2022 (i.e. about two months after the event):

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

- Link to the YouTube video of EELISA Innovation Talk # 3 hosted by UPB:

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KxD9RPIHQVs&list=PLL20beMSLsd7g5p7RQYm_y_lcXw8i7aZ4&index=3

There were about 60 live participants, of which about eight followed the event live on YouTube and about 52 were present on-site. In sum, the event was much more frequented on-site than online and generated more views on YouTube after than during the event.

2.2.4 EELISA Innovation Talk # 4 hosted by SNS

The fourth EELISA Innovation Talk was hosted by SNS on 26 October 2022 from 17:00-18:00 (CEST) at the Palazzo della Carovana of Scuola Normale Superiore in Pisa. The topic of this fourth EELISA Innovation Talk was “The Electron: A Journey to Discoveries and Innovation”. Organizers from SNS chose the following teaser for the event webpage: “This EELISA Innovation Talk will look at some key technologies that originated from the discovery of the electron in 1897 and highlight the new opportunities for innovation. The discussion will use specific examples to illustrate the challenges of transforming knowledge acquired in an academic research environment into innovation and ultimately into a profitable business.” The topic of this fourth EELISA Innovation Talk was dealt with in a talk by Dr. Vittorio Pellegrini (CEO and CIO of BeDimensional S.p.a.). To promote the event the following event webpage and event banner were created:

- Link to the event webpage of EELISA Innovation Talk # 4 hosted by SNS: <https://eelisa.eu/events/innovation-talk-session4-the-electron-a-journey-to-discoveries-and-innovation/>

Figure 6: Event banner for EELISA Innovation Talk # 4 hosted by SNS

This about 60 minutes EELISA Innovation Talk, hosted by SNS, featured a talk by Dr. Vittorio Pellegrini, CEO and CIO of BeDimensional S.p.a. and SNS graduate. Attendance was possible in-person at SNS and online via the live stream on the EELISA YouTube channel.

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

Pellegrini introduced the distinction between discovery and innovation and for the most part of his talk he used the example of the electron to shed some light on the way from one to the other (drawing on a book that he published recently). His main thesis throughout the talk was that the way from discoveries in a research environment to market-ready innovation implemented by startups and businesses is very challenging indeed. In fact, those making the discoveries and those innovating are oftentimes altogether different people. In the main part of his talk Pellegrini went through several examples in order to elucidate the link between discoveries and innovation.

The first example was the discovery of the electron by J. J. Thomson on 30 April 1897. Today's main technology that arose from this discovery is electronic computing technology. Pellegrini went through the main steps (invention of the vacuum tube and later of the transistor) that led from the discovery of the electron to today's computing technology, which showed that the way from basic research to later mass-market innovation is at the time of the first discovery not at all foreseeable. The transistor was a breakthrough innovation on the basis of the original discovery of the electron and allowed for the first profitable companies to be founded on the basis of this innovation. One of the first mass-market devices derived from the original discovery of the electron was the transistor radio, a portable radio which is much smaller than the older vacuum tube radios. Then transistors were improved dramatically: they decreased in size and production cost and increased dramatically in computing power up to today's microchips (according to Moore's law the number of transistors on microchips doubles every two years). A single-atom transistor would be the ultimate limit of the computing unit. Generally, the evolution of computing power is at the basis of today's essential eight technologies (artificial intelligence, augmented reality, blockchain, drones, the internet of things, robotics, virtual reality, and 3-D printing). According to Pellegrini, the future of these technological developments lies in the innovations based on Albert Einstein's discovery of the photoelectric effect. From this discovery, the innovation of quantum computation is in the process of evolving which can potentially go beyond the limit of the single atom set in transistor computing by using quantum bits. The first quantum computing startups are currently entering the market.

Other examples Pellegrini used to illustrate the challenging way from discovery to innovation were the x-ray, the laser, aluminum, and finally graphene, on which the innovation of his own company, BeDimensional, is based. BeDimensional is able to produce graphene on a large scale in a patented way to be used in lithium-ion batteries indispensable for e-mobility. The company combines graphene and silicon to produce even more efficient silicon-graphene batteries and is on the way to offer new market-ready products that will improve people's lives.

The EELISA Innovation Talk # 4 hosted by SNS is available on the EELISA YouTube channel and has 156 views and one like as of November 2022 (i.e. about one month after the event):

- Link to the YouTube video of EELISA Innovation Talk # 4 hosted by SNS: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KvJE9qpBsZM&list=PLL20beMSLsd7g5p7RQYm_y_lcXw8i7aZ4&index=4

There were about 37 live participants, of which about twelve followed the event live on YouTube and about 25 were present on-site. In sum, the event was more frequented on-site than online and generated more views on YouTube after than during the event.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

2.2.5 EELISA Innovation Talk # 5 hosted by SSSA

The fifth EELISA Innovation Talk was hosted by SSSA on 21 November 2022 from 15:00-18:30 (CEST) in the Aula magna in Pisa. The topic of this fifth EELISA Innovation Talk was “Open Innovation: From Lab to Market”. Organizers from SSSA chose the following teaser for the event webpage: “Blended Webinar for students, researchers, Phd and general public on the following themes: 1. Innovation and open innovation (what is it, what are the pros and cons of the scheme). 2. IUVO case study (exoskeletons from lab to market). 3. Structured interview to better analyse the IUVO case.” The topic of this fifth EELISA Innovation Talk was covered in a blended webinar by Prof. Alberto Di Minin (Full Professor of Management at SSSA) and Prof. Nicola Vitiello (Full Professor of the BioRobotics Institute at SSSA and co-founder of the spin-off company IUVO S.R.L.). To promote the event the following event webpage and event banner were created:

- Link to the event webpage of EELISA Innovation Talk # 5 hosted by SSSA: <https://eelisa.eu/events/innovation-talk-session5-open-innovation-from-lab-to-market/>

Figure 7: Event banner for EELISA Innovation Talk # 5 hosted by SSSA

This about 60 minutes EELISA Innovation Talk, hosted by SSSA, featured a conversation between Prof. Alberto Di Minin, Professor of Management at SSSA, and Prof. Nicola Vitiello, Professor of the BioRobotics Institute at SSSA and co-founder of the spin-off company IUVO S.R.L. The conversation under the title “Open Innovation: From Lab to Market” was about how researchers can transform their knowledge into innovative products. Attendance was possible in-person at SSSA and online via the live stream on the EELISA YouTube channel.

Vitiello started his scientific career 15 years ago in the field of wearable robotics. In 2015, he founded his company, IUVO, which manufactures wearable robotic devices for the medical, fitness and industrial sectors. Today, his company has 20 employees. Based on Vitiello’s own journey from lab to innovation, the talk explained seven key aspects of this transformation process. These are crucial because according to Vitiello good technology alone is not enough as there are many obstacles besides the technology itself: “In an open innovation process, only 5 to 10 percent is about the technology itself. The rest is about how it can be implemented

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

in the market. This is where researchers need to build new competences and bring in external experts for support." The seven key aspects of the transformation process from lab to market are as follows:

1. Find a clearly defined application for your technology: The technology alone is not the innovation. It's about whether you can apply the technology in practice to solve real problems. So you have to select technologies according to their fields of application. Not all technologies that are developed in science are also suitable for the innovation process.
2. Manage the complexity of multidisciplinary: Many different sciences are often involved in the development of a technology, making the process very complex. In wearable robotics, for example, psychologists, doctors, and various engineers worked together to develop the first prototype. The innovation process can only be successful through good cooperation. To achieve this, the innovator must successfully coordinate the involved parties.
3. Involvement and role of third parties: Since the innovation process is not just about technology, as a researcher you need the help of external experts. Vitiello's advice is that you look for suitable partners who can help you with management, legal issues or their knowledge of the market. This cooperation should be characterized by trust, especially in the beginning, and can later be laid down in contracts.
4. Involvement and role of industrial partners: Partners from the business world can help to put the ideas and energy of the young entrepreneurs into a solid structure. They support with their management know-how and thus reduce the entrepreneurial risk.
5. Changing roles and how to stay focused: During the innovation process, the roles of the people involved change naturally: Scientists become entrepreneurs, but not necessarily CEOs; investors become managers. At this point, innovations often fail. It is important to adapt to the changes and not lose sight of the actual mission.
6. Scaling up: The process of scaling up from a startup to an established company is also very delicate and something where many innovation journeys fail. In order to master this challenge, it is very important to deal intensively with the application area right at the beginning of the process and to develop a business model on that basis.
7. Know and show the value of your product: To successfully establish the technologies on the market, the value of the product must be clear and visible. This added value must be defined specifically for each user group, for example in a return of investment report.

After the talk, there was the possibility to ask questions online in the chat and on-site.

The EELISA Innovation Talk # 5 hosted by SSSA is available on the EELISA YouTube channel and has 78 views and 3 likes as of November 2022 (i.e. the month of the event):

- Link to the YouTube video of EELISA Innovation Talk # 5 hosted by SSSA:
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=HHJjPx19zj4>

There were about 22 live participants, of which about 12 followed the event live on YouTube and about 10 were present on-site. In sum, the event was more frequented online than on-site.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

2.2.6 Summary overview of the on-site and online participation in all EELISA Innovation Talks during the first reporting period

Number and Host of EELISA Innovation Talk	Live Participants on-site	Live participants online	Views on YouTube (as of Nov. 2022)	Likes on YouTube (as of Nov. 2022)	Comments on YouTube (as of Nov. 2022)
Innovation Talk # 1 hosted by BME	20	15	90	1	0
Innovation Talk # 2 hosted by FAU	20	40	521	20	1
Innovation Talk # 3 hosted by UPB	52	8	204	6	1
Innovation Talk # 4 hosted by SNS	25	12	156	1	0
Innovation Talk # 5 hosted by SSSA	10	12	78	3	0

Table 2: Summary overview of the on-site and online participation in all EELISA Innovation Talks during the first reporting period

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811